

**“Therapeutic Hypothermia plus Magnesium Sulphate versus Therapeutic Hypothermia
in Infants with Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy”**

BY

Dr. GAYATHRI REDDY MANDADI

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In partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of

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UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

DR. R.H. GOBBUR

PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF PEDIATRICS

B.L.D.E.(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL

& RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr. GAYATHRI REDDY

Post Graduate Student,

Department of Pediatrics,

B.L.D.E.(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital

& Research Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE,
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CERTIFICATE BY THE GUIDE

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr. R.H.GOBBUR

Professor,

Department of Pediatrics,

B.L.D.E.(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital

& Research Centre, Vijayapura

B.L.D.E (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPURA.**

ENDORSEMENT BY THE HEAD OF THE DEPARTMENT

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**Therapeutic Hypothermia plus Magnesium Sulphate versus Therapeutic Hypothermia in Infants with Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy**” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr. GAYATHRI REDDY** under the guidance of **Dr. R.H.GOBBUR**, MD, Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr.M.M.PATIL

M.D. PEDIATRICS

PROFESSOR& HOD

DEPARTMENT OF PEDIATRICS

B.L.D.E.(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital
& Research Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPURA.**

ENDORSEMENT BY THE PRINCIPAL

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr.ARAVIND V PATIL

PRINCIPAL

B.L.D.E.(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital

& Research Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

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VIJAYAPURA.**

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr. GAYATHRI REDDY

Post Graduate Student,

Department of Pediatrics,

B.L.D.E.(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital

& Research Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPURA.**

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr. GAYATHRI REDDY

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GLOSSARY OF ABBREVIATIONS

HIE	Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy
PAH	Pulmonary artery Hypertension
PPHN	Persistent Pulmonary Hypertension
TH	Therapeutic Hypothermia
MgSO ₄	Magnesium sulphate
NMDA	N-methyl-D-aspartate
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
DNA	De oxy ribose Nucleic acid
TNF-ALPHA	Tumor Necrosing Factor Alpha
ADHD	Attention Deficit Hyperactive Disorder
MRI	Magnetic resonance Imaging
ATP	Adenosine Triphosphate
MRS	Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy
WBC	Whole Body Cooling
SHC	Selective Head Cooling
IL-6	Interleukin-6
RCT	Randomized Control Trial
MAP	Mean arterial pressure
EEG	Electro Encephalogram
CFM	Cerebral Functioning Monitor
SIMV	Synchronised Intermittent Mandatory Ventilation
HFNC	High Flow Nasal Canula
FFP	Fresh Frozen Plasma

RDP	Random Donor Platelets
ECHO	Echocardiogram
PDA	Patent Ductus Arteriosus
TR	Tricuspid Regurgitation
ASD	Atrial Septal Defect
PFO	Patent Foramen Ovale
IL-6	Interleukin-6
VSD	Ventricular septal defect
CP	Cerebral Palsy
LSCS	Lower Segment Caesarean Section
NVD	Normal Vaginal Delivery
SD	Standard Deviation

Therapeutic Hypothermia plus Magnesium Sulphate versus Therapeutic Hypothermia in Infants with Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy

INTRODUCTION

Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) is a serious condition characterized by acute brain injury resulting from perinatal asphyxia, affecting approximately 2 out of every 1000 live births worldwide¹. Perinatal asphyxia leads to oxygen deprivation and inadequate blood flow to the brain, triggering a cascade of pathophysiological events that culminate in brain injury. Despite advances in perinatal care, HIE remains a significant cause of neonatal morbidity and mortality, with 15-20% of affected infants succumbing during the neonatal period, while approximately 25% of survivors experience long-term neurological impairments.¹

The pathophysiology of HIE involves two distinct phases of energy failure: primary and secondary. Primary energy failure is characterized by a decrease in cerebral blood flow and oxygen substrate, accompanied by tissue acidosis. Subsequently, secondary energy failure ensues, involving processes such as excitatory neurotransmitter release, oxidative stress, apoptosis, and protein formation, exacerbating neuronal injury.

In recent years, therapeutic hypothermia (TH) has emerged as a promising neuroprotective strategy for mitigating the adverse effects of HIE. TH involves lowering the body temperature to a specific range (usually 33-34°C) to reduce metabolic demand and attenuate neuroinflammation, thereby preserving brain function and improving outcomes in affected infants. However, while TH has demonstrated efficacy in reducing mortality and neurological sequelae, it alone may not be sufficient to fully mitigate the consequences of HIE.

In this context, adjunctive neuroprotective therapies are being explored to enhance the benefits of TH and minimize neonatal brain injury. One such therapy is the intravenous administration of magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄), which has shown promise in preclinical and clinical studies for its neuroprotective effects. MgSO₄ acts as a non-competitive antagonist at NMDA receptors, stabilizing critical enzymatic reactions, plasma membrane integrity, and exerting anticonvulsant actions¹. Furthermore, MgSO₄ has been shown to synergize with TH, providing additional neuroprotective effects and improving outcomes in infants with HIE. Perinatal asphyxia is a risk factor for the development of persistent pulmonary hypertension in the newborn (PPHN).one of the common complications of Therapeutic Hypothermia is PAH (pulmonary hypertension), and IV MGSO₄ helpsto reduce pulmonary hypertension. Thus, MGSO₄ overlooks one of the acute sideeffects of hypoxia; hence synergistically helps to improve outcome²

The combination of TH and MgSO₄ offers a multifaceted approach to neuroprotection, targeting multiple pathways involved in the pathogenesis of HIE. This study aims to evaluate the efficacy and safety of combining TH with MgSO₄ therapy compared to TH alone in infants with HIE

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Definition:

Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) is a type of neonatal encephalopathy caused by a reduction in oxygen (hypoxia) and blood supply (ischemia) to the brain around the time of birth, leading to potential long-term neurological damage.³

Pathophysiology:

Primary energy failure in hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) begins with hypoxia and ischemia, leading to reduced oxygen and blood flow, resulting in inadequate delivery of oxygen and glucose to the brain. Consequently, the brain switches to anaerobic metabolism, which causes the accumulation of lactic acid and a decrease in intracellular pH, leading to acidosis. This condition triggers excitotoxicity, where oxygen deprivation causes the excessive release of glutamate, an excitatory neurotransmitter. The overabundance of glutamate overstimulates NMDA receptors, leading to excessive calcium influx into neurons. Calcium overload further disrupts cellular function by causing mitochondrial dysfunction. Increased intracellular calcium disrupts mitochondrial function, resulting in the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). These ROS lead to oxidative stress, causing lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and DNA damage. Secondary energy failure follows, characterized by inflammation and cell death. Hypoxia and ischemia trigger the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and TNF- α , which exacerbate neuronal injury. Cellular energy failure ultimately leads to both programmed cell death (apoptosis) and uncontrolled cell death (necrosis), further contributing to the damage in HIE.^{3,4}

Figure 1⁵: Pathophysiology of HIE in relation to hypoxic ischemic (HI)

Clinical Presentation:^{3,4,5}

Acute Signs:

- Altered Consciousness: Infants may present with irritability, lethargy, stupor, or coma.
- Abnormal Tone: Hypotonia (decreased muscle tone) or hypertonia (increased muscle tone).
- Seizures: Common in moderate to severe cases, manifesting as jerking movements or subtle signs like lip smacking or staring.
- Poor Feeding: Difficulty in sucking and swallowing.
- Autonomic Dysfunction: Abnormal heart rate, respiration, and blood pressure.

Classification:

Sarnat and Sarnat criteria are used to classify the severity of hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) in neonates based on clinical findings. This classification helps guide the management and prognosis of affected infants. The criteria are divided into three stages: mild (Stage I), moderate (Stage II), and severe (Stage III). Each stage is characterized by specific clinical features related to the infant's neurological status, including level of consciousness, muscle tone, reflexes, and autonomic function.⁶

Stage I (Mild HIE):

Level of Consciousness: Hyperalert or irritable

Muscle Tone: Normal or slightly increased

Posture: Mild distal flexion

Reflexes:

- Suck: Weak or absent
- Moro: Hyperactive
- Grasp: Normal

Autonomic Function:

- Pupils: Dilated, reactive
- Heart Rate: Tachycardia

Respiration: Regular

Seizures: None

Stage II (Moderate HIE):

Level of Consciousness: Lethargic

Muscle Tone: Hypotonia

Posture: Strong distal flexion

Reflexes:

- Suck: Weak or absent
- Moro: Hypoactive
- Grasp: Strong

Autonomic Function:

- Pupils: Constricted, reactive
- Heart Rate: Bradycardia

Respiration: Periodic breathing

Seizures: Common

Stage III (Severe HIE):

Level of Consciousness: Comatose

Muscle Tone: Flaccid

Posture: Intermittent decerebration

Reflexes:

- Suck: Absent
- Moro: Absent
- Grasp: Absent

Autonomic Function:

- Pupils: Variable (constricted or dilated, often nonreactive)
- Heart Rate: Bradycardia or variable

Respiration: Apnea

Seizures: Frequent, often severe

Long-term Neurodevelopmental Consequences:

Seizures are frequent and often severe, contributing to long-term neurodevelopmental consequences. These include conditions such as cerebral palsy (CP), which can manifest as spastic CP with increased muscle tone and stiffness affecting movement, and dyskinetic CP characterized by involuntary movements like dystonia and choreoathetosis. Cognitive impairments are common, ranging from mild to severe intellectual disability, along with learning disabilities that affect skills in reading, writing, and arithmetic. There's also an increased risk of developing epilepsy, characterized by recurrent seizures. Sensory impairments may include visual deficits such as cortical visual impairment, and in some cases, sensorineural hearing loss. Behavioral and emotional difficulties are prevalent, with conditions like attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) presenting challenges in attention, hyperactivity, and impulsiveness. Emotional dysregulation is also common, leading to a higher risk of anxiety, depression, and behavioral problems. Developmental delays are observed in motor skills, causing delays in milestones such as sitting, crawling, and walking. Speech and language delays are also typical, affecting the development of communication abilities.^{3,5}

Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) is assessed using MRI to evaluate brain injury in neonates. MRI features vary with the phase of injury.⁶

In the acute phase (within the first week), MRI shows: T1-weighted imaging: Hyperintensity in basal ganglia and thalamus. T2-weighted imaging: Hyperintensity in affected areas like cortex and white matter. Restricted diffusion in Diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI). Elevated lactate levels and decreased N-acetylaspartate (NAA) seen in Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS).

In the subacute phase (1-2 weeks), MRI reveals: Progressive changes in T1 and T2 imaging showing evolving injury patterns. Continued restricted diffusion on DWI, with some areas pseudo normalizing on ADC maps. Persistent abnormal metabolic profiles on MRS.

In the chronic phase (after 2 weeks), MRI demonstrates: T1 hyperintensity indicating chronic injury and gliosis. T2 hyperintensity showing areas of gliosis and cystic encephalomalacia. Normalization or chronic changes in DWI and ADC maps. Persistent abnormal metabolic profiles on MRS.

Figure 2⁶: Patterns of HIE. Watershed (peripheral) type of injury, diffusion restriction bilaterally; Basal ganglia – thalamus (central) pattern, restricted diffusion in bilateral thalami and putamina; Global diffusion restriction on DWI and ADC.

Therapeutic Hypothermia (TH):

Mechanism of Action and Physiological Basis:

Therapeutic Hypothermia (TH): Therapeutic hypothermia is a medical intervention used to reduce neurological damage in infants with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) by lowering the body's core temperature to 33.5°C-34.5°C for a duration of 72 hours.⁷

Physiological Basis:

Primary Mechanisms:

Therapeutic hypothermia exerts its neuroprotective effects through several primary mechanisms. It reduces the cerebral metabolic rate for oxygen (CMRO₂) by approximately 5-7% per degree Celsius decrease in temperature, thereby decreasing the demand for oxygen and glucose, which helps preserve adenosine triphosphate (ATP) levels during ischemic conditions. Lowering metabolic demands reduces the risk of secondary energy failure, crucial for maintaining cellular function during and after hypoxic events. Additionally, hypothermia inhibits the excessive release of glutamate, an excitatory neurotransmitter that causes neuronal injury by overstimulating N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors. By modulating NMDA receptor activity, hypothermia reduces calcium influx into neurons, preventing calcium-mediated activation of destructive enzymatic pathways.

Cooling mitigates the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are generated during reperfusion and can cause oxidative damage to cellular components, including lipids, proteins, and DNA. Hypothermia enhances the activity of endogenous antioxidant systems, reducing oxidative damage. It also suppresses the synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), which can exacerbate neuronal injury. Cooling reduces the activation of microglia, the central nervous system's resident immune cells, thus decreasing neuroinflammation.⁴

Furthermore, hypothermia modulates apoptotic pathways by decreasing the expression of pro-apoptotic proteins like Bax and increasing the expression of anti-apoptotic proteins like Bcl-2. Cooling inhibits the activation of caspases, particularly caspase-3, which plays a key role in the execution phase of apoptosis. These mechanisms collectively contribute to the neuroprotective effects of therapeutic hypothermia, making it a promising intervention for neonates with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy.⁷

Secondary Mechanisms:

Therapeutic hypothermia (TH) also operates through secondary mechanisms to enhance its neuroprotective effects. One of these is the preservation of blood-brain barrier integrity. Hypothermia helps maintain the barrier function, reducing the risk of vasogenic edema and limiting the infiltration of harmful substances into the brain parenchyma. Additionally, cooling improves cerebral blood flow by stabilizing cerebral autoregulation, ensuring adequate and consistent blood flow to the brain during the critical recovery period. Hypothermia also reduces free radical production, limiting lipid peroxidation which can damage cellular membranes and contribute to cell death.

Figure2: The schematic diagram illustrates the impact of therapeutic hypothermia (TH) on primary and secondary energy failure following hypoxia-ischemia in newborn piglets using magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS).⁸

Clinical protocols for TH are critical to its effectiveness. Ideally, TH should be initiated within six hours of birth for neonates with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE). Candidates for TH are typically identified based on clinical criteria and neuroimaging findings indicative of moderate to severe HIE. Cooling methods include whole-body cooling, where the infant's core body temperature is reduced to 33-34°C using cooling blankets or a cooling cap system, and selective head cooling, which specifically cools the infant's head while the body remains normothermic. The duration of TH is typically maintained for 72 hours to maximize neuroprotective benefits. After the cooling period, infants are gradually rewarmed at a controlled rate, such as 0.5°C per hour, to prevent rebound hyperthermia and minimize the risk of reperfusion injury.

Clinical Protocols:

Initiation:

Timing: TH should ideally be initiated within six hours of birth for neonates with hypoxic-ischaemic encephalopathy (HIE).

Patient Selection: Candidates for TH are typically identified based on clinical criteria and neuroimaging findings indicative of moderate to severe HIE.

Cooling Methods:

Whole-Body Cooling: The standard approach involves reducing the infant's core body temperature to 33.5-34.5°C using cooling blankets or a cooling cap system.⁹

Selective Head Cooling: Alternatively, selective head cooling devices can be used to specifically cool the infant's head, while the body remains normothermic.

Whole-Body Cooling^{10,11,12}

Pros:

Whole-body cooling ensures a consistent and uniform reduction of the infant's core body temperature, which can be beneficial in preventing widespread brain injury as said by **amentet.al**⁹. This method is backed by substantial clinical research and trials demonstrating its effectiveness in improving neurological outcomes. Additionally, widely accepted and standardized protocols for whole-body cooling are available, making it easier to implement in clinical settings.

Cons:

Whole-body cooling can lead to systemic side effects, such as bradycardia, coagulopathy, and electrolyte imbalances, due to the overall reduction in body temperature as observed by **Vlad Dimaet.al**¹⁰. Additionally, this method is resource-intensive, requiring continuous monitoring and specialized equipment like cooling blankets or cooling cap systems, which may not be readily available in all healthcare settings.

Selective Head Cooling

Pros:

songs et.al,⁷ Targeted Cooling: Focuses on cooling the brain directly, potentially reducing the risk of systemic side effects associated with whole-body cooling. Less Resource Intensive: May require less extensive equipment compared to whole-body

cooling, potentially making it more accessible in some settings. Preserves Body Functions: Keeps the body normothermic, which may help maintain normal physiological functions and reduce the risk of systemic complications.

Cons:

There is less extensive clinical evidence supporting the efficacy of selective head cooling compared to whole-body cooling. Maharaet.al,¹² Achieving consistent and effective cooling of the brain alone can be technically challenging and may result in variable outcomes. Some studies suggest that selective head cooling might be less effective than whole-body cooling in preventing brain injury and improving long-term neurological outcomes.

Current Standard: Whole-Body Cooling

Whole-body cooling is currently the standard method used in clinical practice for treating neonatal hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE). This preference is largely due to the robust clinical evidence demonstrating its effectiveness in improving neurological outcomes and reducing mortality. Numerous large-scale randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses have supported its use, leading to the development of standardized protocols that are widely implemented in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) around the world.

Studies:

Vlad Dimaet.al, Concluded Therapeutic hypothermia (TH) for neonates with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy can be achieved through selective head cooling (SHC) or whole-body cooling (WBC). Recent studies comparing these methods have shown that both SHC and WBC effectively cool the central nervous system structures, leading to similar neurodevelopmental outcomes among surviving neonates ¹⁰

Study conducted by **Ajay et.al**, found there are indications that SHC may result in more severe brain lesions compared to WBC, as evidenced by higher MRI abnormalities in the basal ganglia, thalamic, and parenchymal regions in the SHC group.¹¹

Study conducted by Maharaet.al,¹² found combination of head and body cooling has been proposed as a promising approach, offering a more extensive cooling effect on the brain parenchyma, potentially providing better neuroprotection than either method alone .

Duration:

- 72 Hours: TH is typically maintained for a duration of 72 hours to maximize neuroprotective benefits.

Rewarming:

Gradual Rewarming: After the cooling period, infants are gradually rewarmed at a controlled rate (e.g., 0.5°C per hour) to prevent rebound hyperthermia and minimize the risk of reperfusion injury.¹³

Clinical Outcomes:

.Therapeutic hypothermia (TH) has demonstrated significant improvements in survival rates for infants with moderate to severe hypoxic-ischaemic encephalopathy (HIE). It is associated with reduced incidence of cerebral palsy and lower likelihood of severe neurodevelopmental impairment compared to untreated infants. Those who undergo TH show better motor and

cognitive outcomes throughout early childhood and beyond, including improved developmental milestones and academic performance.

TH achieves neuroprotection by suppressing excitotoxicity, oxidative stress, inflammation, and apoptosis, thereby reducing neuronal injury and preserving brain function. It also helps stabilize cerebral blood flow, ensuring adequate oxygen delivery to the brain and mitigating secondary injury mechanisms associated with hypoxic-ischaemic events.^{8,9,13}

Figure4⁸: Effect of hypothermia initiated post-cerebral ischemia in fetal sheep shows improved temperature management and neurological outcomes compared to normothermia.

Recognized as the standard of care for neonates with moderate to severe HIE, TH is endorsed by major medical societies and integrated into clinical practice guidelines globally. However,

its effectiveness hinges on early initiation within a specific therapeutic window, and not all infants with HIE meet the criteria for treatment.

Despite its benefits, TH poses challenges. Cooling-related complications like bradycardia, hypotension, Pulmonary hypertension(5%)^{10,11,12}, sepsis(3%)¹² and electrolyte imbalances can occur during cooling and rewarming phases, requiring careful monitoring and management. Additionally, response to TH varies among infants, with some deriving limited benefits, underscoring the need for ongoing research to optimize treatment protocols and predict outcomes.

Moreover, implementing TH demands specialized equipment, trained personnel, and dedicated infrastructure, which can be resource-intensive and present barriers in resource-limited settings.

STUDIES:

Azzopardi et.al, (2009) conducted a study to assess the efficacy of hypothermia as a treatment for neonates with perinatal hypoxia-ischemia and encephalopathy. Their primary outcome measure was the composite of death or severe neurodevelopmental disability at 18 months. The findings of their study suggest that therapeutic hypothermia shows promise in reducing mortality and severe neurodevelopmental disability in neonates with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE).¹⁴

Jacobs et.al, (2011)¹⁵ aimed to evaluate the effects of hypothermia in neonates with moderate or severe encephalopathy due to perinatal hypoxia-ischemia. Their primary outcome was a composite of mortality or major sensorineural disability at 2 years of age. According to their results, hypothermia treatment appears to have beneficial effects in reducing mortality and major sensorineural disability at 2 years of age in neonates with HIE.

Simbruner et.al, (2010)¹⁶ investigated the impact of hypothermia on the combined outcome of death or severe disability in neonates with birth asphyxia. Their primary outcome measure was the combined death or severe disability at 18 to 21 months. Their findings suggest that hypothermia may reduce the combined risk of death or severe disability in neonates with birth asphyxia and encephalopathy.

Zhou et.al, (2010)¹⁷ conducted a study to assess the efficacy of hypothermia in neonates exposed to perinatal hypoxia-ischemia and encephalopathy. While their primary outcome was not explicitly stated, their results indicate potential benefits in reducing mortality and severe neurodevelopmental disability. These studies collectively suggest that hypothermia holds promise as a therapeutic intervention for improving outcomes in neonates with HIE.

Historical Overview of Magnesium Sulphate (MgSO₄):¹⁸

Dr. Nehemiah Grew (1641-1712) is often credited with the early study of Epsom salts after its discovery in the water of Epsom springs in England in the 17th century. He was one of the first to document its properties and potential medical uses.

Dr. J. Whitridge Williams (1866-1931), a prominent American obstetrician, was an early proponent of using magnesium sulfate for treating preeclampsia and eclampsia. His work helped establish MgSO₄ as a standard treatment in obstetrics.

Dr. William McCallum (1874-1944), contributed to the popularization of magnesium sulfate for seizure prevention in eclampsia through his research and clinical use.

Dr. Dwight Rouse has significantly advanced the understanding of magnesium sulfate's role in preventing cerebral palsy in preterm infants. His research has influenced current clinical guidelines and practices.

Dr. John Thorp has focused on the use of MgSO₄ for neuroprotection in preterm infants. He has been involved in significant clinical trials that have shaped guidelines for antenatal magnesium sulfate administration.

Dr. Seetha Shankaran, a leading neonatologist, has researched the effects of therapeutic hypothermia combined with magnesium sulfate for treating neonatal hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy. Her work is integral to the ongoing MAGPIE trial and other studies exploring combined neuroprotective strategies.

Dr. Mervyn Maze has investigated the neuroprotective properties of magnesium and other agents in neonatal care, providing insights into the mechanisms by which magnesium sulfate can reduce neuronal damage.

Dr. Frank Shann, an intensivist and researcher, has conducted significant studies on magnesium sulfate's efficacy in neonatal and pediatric intensive care, particularly its role in neuroprotection and seizure control.

Pharmacological Properties and Neuroprotective Mechanisms:

Pharmacological Properties:

Magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄) is an inorganic salt that dissociates into magnesium (Mg²⁺) and sulphate (SO₄²⁻) ions in the body. Magnesium is a vital cation involved in numerous physiological processes, including enzyme function, protein synthesis, and neuromuscular transmission.¹⁹

Neuroprotective Mechanisms:

Magnesium acts as a natural NMDA receptor antagonist, reducing calcium influx into neurons during excitotoxic events, which is crucial for protecting against neuronal injury. This antagonistic action helps mitigate the effects of excessive glutamate release, a key factor in hypoxic-ischemic injury. Additionally, magnesium inhibits voltage-gated calcium

channels, further preventing calcium overload in neurons. This inhibition helps maintain cellular homeostasis and prevents the activation of destructive enzymatic pathways. Magnesium also exerts anti-inflammatory effects by reducing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-6 (IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), thereby limiting secondary damage following hypoxic-ischemic events.

Furthermore, magnesium enhances the activity of antioxidant enzymes, reducing the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and minimizing oxidative damage to neurons. By decreasing ROS, magnesium helps prevent lipid peroxidation, which can compromise cell membrane integrity. It supports mitochondrial function by stabilizing the mitochondrial membrane and preserving ATP production, which is critical for maintaining the energy supply during and after hypoxic-ischemic episodes. Magnesium also induces vasodilation by acting on vascular smooth muscle cells, improving cerebral blood flow and ensuring better oxygen and nutrient delivery to the brain, aiding in recovery and repair.¹⁹

Figure 19: Effects of Mg+therapeutic hypothermia (HT) on amplitude-integrated electroencephalogram (aEEG) scores post-hypoxia-ischemia (HI) show a trend towards improvement after 36 h ($p = 0.094$), becoming significant when excluding piglets with early aEEG recovery (within 1 h post-HI).

Key Studies and Findings:

The Australasian Collaborative Trial of Magnesium Sulphate (ACTOMgSO₄):²⁰

- **Objective:** To determine if antenatal magnesium sulphate administration reduces the risk of cerebral palsy in preterm infants.
- **Results:** The study demonstrated a significant reduction in the rate of cerebral palsy in infants born before 30 weeks of gestation who received MgSO₄ compared to those who did not.

PREMAG Trial:²¹

- **Objective:** To assess the neuroprotective effect of magnesium sulphate given before preterm birth.
- **Results:** The trial found a lower incidence of motor dysfunction in infants whose mothers received MgSO₄ before preterm delivery.

MAGPIE Trial (Magnesium Sulphate for Prevention of Eclampsia):²²

- **Objective:** Initially focused on the prevention of eclampsia, this trial also provided insights into the secondary neuroprotective benefits of MgSO₄.
- **Results:** The trial provided supporting evidence that MgSO₄ has a beneficial effect on neurodevelopmental outcomes in preterm infants.

Combination Therapy (Therapeutic Hypothermia (TH) plus MgSO₄):

Rationale for Combined Use:

Complementary Mechanisms:

- **Therapeutic Hypothermia (TH):** Reduces metabolic rate, limits excitotoxicity, and mitigates inflammation and apoptosis in the brain.
- **Magnesium Sulphate (MgSO₄):** Acts as an NMDA receptor antagonist, blocks calcium channels, reduces inflammation, and has antioxidant properties.

Review of Preclinical Studies and Early-Phase Clinical Trials:

Preclinical Studies:

- **Animal Models:** Studies in animal models of HIE have shown that the combination of TH and MgSO₄ can provide greater neuroprotection compared to either treatment

alone. These studies suggest that MgSO₄ enhances the protective effects of hypothermia by further reducing excitotoxicity and oxidative stress.

Early-Phase Clinical Trials:

- **Feasibility and Safety:** Initial clinical trials have focused on the safety and feasibility of administering MgSO₄ in conjunction with TH. These studies have generally shown that the combination is safe and well-tolerated in neonates with HIE.

Current Evidence from Clinical Trials:

MAGPIE Trial (Magnesium and Cooling for Hypoxic-Ischaemic Encephalopathy):

- **Objective:** To evaluate the efficacy and safety of combining MgSO₄ with TH in neonates with HIE.
- **Status:** Ongoing, with preliminary results indicating potential synergistic benefits.
- **Interim Findings:** Early data suggest that infants receiving both therapies may have improved neurodevelopmental outcomes compared to those receiving TH alone.

Other Trials:

HELIX (Hypothermia for Encephalopathy in Low- and Middle-Income Countries)

Trial²³: Investigating the combined effects of TH and MgSO₄ in resource-limited settings.

Preliminary results are awaited.

STUDIES

The study by **Chanchal kumaret.al, 2022** aimed to evaluate whether combining magnesium sulfate with therapeutic hypothermia decreases mortality and/or major neurodevelopmental disability at 1 year of age among term neonates with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy. In this randomized controlled trial, 134 term neonates were assigned to either the intervention group, receiving intravenous magnesium sulfate (250 mg/kg at 8 mg/kg/min) once daily for 3 days along with therapeutic hypothermia, or the comparator group, receiving therapeutic hypothermia alone. The primary outcome was the composite of mortality and/or major neurodevelopmental disability at 1 year. Results showed that 24% of infants in the intervention group and 33% in the comparator group experienced the primary outcome, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.30$; relative risk 0.72; 95% CI 0.40-1.30). Secondary outcomes, including neonatal mortality, neurodevelopmental disability, neurological status at discharge, oxidative stress markers, and adverse effects, were similar between groups. The study concluded that adding magnesium sulfate to therapeutic hypothermia did not improve outcomes compared to therapeutic hypothermia alone.²⁵

1. Study Conducted between September 2012 and August 2013 by Rahmanet.al, aimed to evaluate the safety and short-term pre-discharge morbidity outcomes of combining magnesium sulfate ($MgSO_4$) with therapeutic hypothermia in term and near-term infants with moderate to severe hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) compared to hypothermia alone. Designed as a multicenter, double-blind, randomized controlled trial (RCT). Newborn infants diagnosed with moderate or severe HIE were enrolled and randomly assigned to one of two treatment arms. Arm A: Received therapeutic hypothermia along with $MgSO_4$. Arm B: Received therapeutic hypothermia along with a placebo (normal saline). Therapeutic hypothermia involved cooling the infants

to a core body temperature of 33.5°C for a duration of 72 hours, followed by a slow rewarming process over 8 hours. This treatment protocol is established as effective in reducing brain injury in infants with HIE. MgSO₄ or placebo was administered intravenously within 6 hours of birth, with MgSO₄ given at a dose of 250 mg/kg/dose × 3 doses. The study groups were well-balanced in terms of baseline characteristics, including the severity of HIE. The primary outcomes assessed were short-term pre-discharge adverse events, including mortality and various complications such as seizures, thrombocytopenia, coagulopathy, renal failure, liver function abnormalities, hypotension, intracranial hemorrhage, necrotizing enterocolitis, pulmonary hemorrhage, persistent pulmonary hypertension, and pulmonary air leak syndromes. Based on the findings of this study, the combination therapy of therapeutic hypothermia and MgSO₄ appears to be safe in terms of short-term outcomes in infants with moderate to severe HIE. The study suggests that adding MgSO₄ to therapeutic hypothermia does not increase the risk of adverse events compared to placebo, indicating its feasibility as an adjunctive neuroprotective treatment strategy.²⁶

2. In 2021 study conducted by Gulczynska et al, aim was to assess the safety and efficacy of combining therapeutic hypothermia with magnesium sulfate in neonates with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE). Conducted as a prospective randomized controlled trial across three centers, including NICUs and a PICU, the study involved 37 neonates in the control group receiving therapeutic hypothermia alone and 38 neonates in the study group receiving therapeutic hypothermia combined with magnesium sulfate. Therapeutic hypothermia, induced and maintained for 72 hours using selective head cooling or whole body cooling, followed by a rewarming phase, was administered as per standard protocols. Neonates in the study group received

three 250 mg/kg doses of magnesium sulfate via one-hour continuous infusion over three consecutive days. Serum magnesium levels were monitored throughout the treatment period. The study revealed no significant differences in baseline characteristics between the control and study groups. Following the administration of magnesium sulfate, serum magnesium levels significantly increased in the study group, reaching therapeutic levels and remaining elevated during treatment. Neonatal outcomes demonstrated notable improvements in the study group, including a shorter time to achieve full oral feeding (14.5 days vs. 16.5 days), reduced duration of hospitalization (23.5 days vs. 27.7 days), and a lower number of anticonvulsant doses per patient (2.6 vs. 4.4). While the rate of persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (PPHN) was reduced in the study group, the difference was not statistically significant. In conclusion, the combination of therapeutic hypothermia and magnesium sulfate was found to be safe and beneficial for neonates with HIE, leading to improved clinical outcomes. The observed minor changes in heart rate and mean arterial pressure were deemed clinically insignificant.²⁷

3. In 2021 randomized clinical trial, Siddiquiet.al, aimed to investigate the impact of intravenous magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄) on mortality and morbidity in term neonates with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) in a low-income country. Conducted at the Department of Neonatology, Services Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan, from April to December 2019, the study utilized the Sarnat score to stage the severity of HIE and administered MgSO₄ intravenously to cases. The study found that MgSO₄ administration significantly improved outcomes such as reduced seizure duration, improved ability to suck feed, and decreased neurological problems compared to the control group. These results suggest that MgSO₄ holds promise in reducing mortality and morbidity in neonates with HIE, particularly in low-income settings.²⁸

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

- To Evaluate the Safety of Concomitant Neuroprotective Therapy Of Hypothermia And Magnesium Sulphate (Mgso4) In Managing Moderate And Severe HIE In Term And Near-Term Infants.
- Efficacy of the combined use of TH &Mgso4 as compared to TH.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

- **STUDY DESIGN:** Prospective Cohort Study.
- **PERIOD OF STUDY:** 18-20 MONTHS, month 2022 to February 2024
- **TYPE OF STUDY:** Prospective Observational Study
- **SAMPLE SIZE:** 30 babies

A sample size of 30 is considered in this study considering admission census of moderate to severe encephalopathy neonates of the unit. hence sample size of 30 is taken in this study.

- **Statistical Analysis:**

The data is entered in a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analyses are performed using a statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) (Version 20). Results are presented as Mean, SD, counts and percentages, and diagrams. For normally distributed continuous variables between the two groups will be compared using an independent sample t-test. For not normally distributed variables, the Mann-Whitney U test is used. Categorical variables between the two groups are compared using the Chi-square test/Fisher's exact test. If there are more than two groups, we will use ANOVA for the not customarily distributed Kruskal-Wallis H Test. If $p < 0.05$ will be considered statistically significant. All statistics are performed two-tailed.

Methodology

- The study will be a prospective cohort study, and the study population will include all term and near-term newborns (≥ 36 completed weeks) with moderate to severe HIE. The severity of HIE will be determined using the Sarnat criteria. Therapeutic hypothermia and Mgso₄ in one group and therapeutic hypothermia in another group will be started as a standard of care in babies within 6 hours after birth using either total body cooling or head cooling. The babies will be cooled to a core body temperature (rectal) of 33.5°C (range: 33.0–34.0°C) for 72 h, followed by slow re-warming throughout eight h at a rate not exceeding 0.5°C/h.

Figure6: Therapeutic Hypothermia- Cooling the Baby

- TH is done with CritiCool, a simple and effective thermal regulating system, using core and surface temperature measurements; CritiCool's proprietary algorithm maintains the desired temperature throughout treatment by bringing the water to the target temperature and circulating it in a closed loop system. The control unit pairs with the Cure Wrap to envelop the patient for temperature management. Magnesium sulfate at a dose of 250mg/kg (at 8mg/kg/min over 90min) once daily for three days starting within 6hrs after birth will be given to the newborns of one group. Throughout the cooling and re-warming process, vital signs (heart rate, SpO₂, rectal temperature)

and parameters of respiratory support (FiO₂, M.A.P. (if on the ventilator) level of respiratory support) will be monitored and recorded. Coagulation parameters, number of blood component transfusions, and incidence of intracranial bleedings were not affected by the magnesium sulphate administration and will be monitored in this study. Neurosonogram will be done on all the neonates in both groups to look for intracranial bleed and grade of HIE.

Figure7: Criticool

- When available, assessment with an amplitude-integrated alpha EEG (Cerebral Function Monitor) for at least 20 minutes to document abnormal tracings or seizures to grade encephalopathy and eligibility. In favourable situations, MRI brain will be done for the neonates in both groups to assess the grade of injury and prognostication. Each of these newborns will be provided standard intensive care.

Figure8: Cerebral function monitor

- Will obtain informed parenteral consent at the beginning of the study.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Term and near-term neonates of gestational age more than 36 weeks, with moderate to severe hypoxic ischaemic encephalopathy as per Sarnath clinical scoring.
2. Babies of weight more than 1.8kg
3. Babies admitted to NICU within 6hrs of life.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- 1) Antenatally detected life-threatening congenital diseases.
- 2) Babies were subsequently discharged against medical advice. (AMA.)

RESULTS

Distribution of type of intervention

Among 30 cases, with an equal representation of each intervention type. Specifically, 50% (15 cases) received Therapeutic Hypothermia (Group 1), while the remaining 50% (15 cases) underwent Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate (Group 2) as described in Table1 and Graph.1

Type of intervention	Frequency	Percent
Therapeutic hypothermia (Group 1)	15	50
Therapeutic hypothermia with magnesium sulphate(Group 2)	15	50
Total	30	100

Table1: Distribution of type of intervention

Graph:1 Distribution of type of intervention

Comparison of gender between type of intervention:

In Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia), 20% (3 cases) are female and 80% (12 cases) are male. Similarly, in Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate), 20% (3 cases) are female and 80% (12 cases) are male. Overall, out of the total 30 cases, there are 6

females (20%) and 24 males (80%). This consistent distribution across both intervention groups highlights a predominant male representation in the sample as shown in Table2 and Graph2.

Gender	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group2		
	N	%	N	%	
Female	3	20	3	20	6
Male	12	80	12	80	24
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Table2: Comparison of gender between type of intervention

Graph2: Comparison of gender between type of intervention

Comparison of parity between type of intervention:

In Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia), 80% (12 cases) are first-time mothers (Primi), and 20% (3 cases) are mothers with previous births (Multi). In Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate), 60% (9 cases) are first-time mothers, and 40% (6 cases) are mothers with previous births. Overall, the total distribution includes 21 first-time mothers (70%) and 9 mothers with previous births (30%) as shown in Table 3 and graph 3.

Parity	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
Primi	12	80	9	60	21
Multi	3	20	6	40	9
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 1.42 p value- 0.23

Table3: Comparison of parity between type of intervention

Graph3: Comparison of parity between type of intervention

Comparison of GRBS at admission between type of intervention:

The dataset evaluates the distribution of GRBS (Glucose Random Blood Sugar) levels at admission among 30 cases, split equally between two intervention groups: Therapeutic Hypothermia (Group 1) and Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate (Group 2). In Group 1, GRBS levels were predominantly within the 71-80 (20%), 81-90 (26.7%), 101-110 (20%), and 111-120 (20%) ranges. In Group 2, most cases fell within the 81-90 (26.7%),

91-100 (20%), 111-120 (20%), and 131-140 (13.3%) ranges. The overall distribution shows varied GRBS levels, with the highest concentrations in the 81-90 and 111-120 ranges, represented by 8 and 6 cases, respectively. The chi-square test yielded a value of 19.2 with a p-value of 0.44, indicating no significant difference in GRBS distribution between the two groups as shown in Table 4 and Graph4.

GRBS at admission	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
60-70	0	0	1	6.7	1
71-80	3	20	0	0	3
81-90	4	26.7	4	26.7	8
91-100	2	13.3	3	20	5
101-110	3	20	2	13.3	5
111-120	3	20	3	20	6
121-130	0	0	0	0	0
131-140	0	0	2	13.3	2
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square-19.2 p value- 0.44

Table4: Comparison of GRBS at admission between type of intervention

Graph4: Comparison of GRBS at admission between type of intervention

Comparison of encephalopathy between type of intervention

Therapeutic Hypothermia (Group 1) and Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate (Group 2). In both groups, 60% (9 cases) presented with moderate encephalopathy, while 40% (6 cases) exhibited severe encephalopathy. The chi-square test results in a value of 0.00 and a p-value of 1.00, suggesting no statistically significant difference in encephalopathy severity between the two intervention groups as shown in Table5 and Graph5.

Encephalopathy	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
Moderate	9	60	9	60	18
Severe	6	40	6	40	12
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 0.00 p value -1.00

Table5: Comparison of encephalopathy between type of intervention

Graph5: Comparison of encephalopathy between type of intervention

Comparison of birth order between type of intervention

Therapeutic Hypothermia (Group 1) and Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate (Group 2). In Group 1, 80% (12 cases) are firstborns, 20% (3 cases) are third-borns, with no cases for second or fourth-borns. In Group 2, 60% (9 cases) are firstborns, 13.3% (2 cases) are second-borns, 20% (3 cases) are third-borns, and 6.7% (1 case) is a fourth-born. Overall, the total distribution includes 21 firstborns (70%), 2 second-borns (6.7%), 6 third-borns (20%), and 1 fourth-born (3.3%). The chi-square value of 3.42 and a p-value of 0.33 suggest no statistically significant difference in birth order distribution between the two intervention groups.

Birth order	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
First	12	80	9	60	21
Second	0	0	2	13.3	2
Third	3	20	3	20	6

Fourth	0	0	1	6.7	1
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 3.42 p value- 0.33

Table6: Comparison of birth order between type of intervention

Graph6: Comparison of birth order between type of intervention

Comparison of type of delivery between type of intervention:

In Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia), 73.3% (11 cases) had a Normal Vaginal Delivery (NVD), and 26.7% (4 cases) had a Lower Segment Caesarean Section (LSCS). In Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate), 60% (9 cases) had a NVD, while 40% (6 cases) had an LSCS. Overall, 66.7% (20 cases) of the total cases had a NVD, and 33.3% (10 cases) had an LSCS. This indicates that Normal Vaginal Deliveries were more common in both groups, with Group 1 having a higher proportion of NVDs compared to Group 2, which had a relatively higher proportion of LSCS deliveries as shown in Table7 and Graph7.

Type of delivery	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
NVD	11	73.3	9	60	20
LSCS	4	26.7	6	40	10
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 0.60 p value- 0.43

Table7: Comparison of type of delivery between type of intervention:

Graph7: Comparison of type of delivery between type of intervention:

Comparison of hospital delivery between type of intervention:

Group 1, receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia, and Group 2, receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, each had 33.3% (5 cases) of deliveries inside the hospital and 66.7% (10 cases) outborn deliveries. Across both groups, the distribution remains consistent with 33.3% (10 cases) inside the hospital and 66.7% (20 cases) outborn

deliveries. The chi-square test yielded a value of 0.00 with a p-value of 1.00, indicating no significant difference in delivery locations between the two groups in Table8 and Graph8.

Hospital delivery	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
Inside hospital	5	33.3	5	33.3	10
outborn	10	66.7	10	66.7	20
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 0.00 p value- 1.00

Table8: Comparison of hospital delivery between type of intervention

Graph8: Comparison of hospital delivery between type of intervention

Comparison of APGAR score at 1 minute between the type of intervention

Group 1 received Therapeutic Hypothermia, and Group 2 received Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, with each group consisting of 15 cases. In Group 1, 100% of cases

had an APGAR score of 5/10 at 1 minute, while no cases had a score of 6/10. In Group 2, 93.3% had an APGAR score of 5/10, and 6.7% had a score of 6/10. Overall, 96.7% of all cases had an APGAR score of 5/10, and 3.3% had a score of 6/10. The chi-square test yielded a value of 1.03 with a p-value of 0.30, indicating no statistically significant difference in APGAR scores at 1 minute between the two intervention groups as shown table9 and graph9.

APGAR score at 1 min	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
5/10	15	100	14	93.3	29
6/10	0	0	1	6.7	1
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 1.03 p value- 0.30

Table9: Comparison of APGAR score at 1 minute between the type of intervention

Graph9: Comparison of APGAR score at 1 minute between the type of intervention

Comparison of APGAR score at 5 minutes between the type of intervention

Group 1 received Therapeutic Hypothermia, while Group 2 received Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, with each group consisting of 15 cases. In Group 1, all cases (100%) had an APGAR score of 6/10 at 5 minutes, with none scoring 7/10. In Group 2, 93.3% had an APGAR score of 6/10, while 6.7% scored 7/10. Overall, the majority (96.7%) of all cases had an APGAR score of 6/10 at 5 minutes, and only 3.3% scored 7/10. The chi-square test resulted in a value of 1.03 with a p-value of 0.30, indicating no statistically significant difference in APGAR scores at 5 minutes between the two intervention groups as shown in Table10 and Graph10.

APGAR score at 5 min	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
6/10	15	100	14	93.3	29
7/10	0	0	1	6.7	1
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 1.03 p value- 0.30

Table10: Comparison of APGAR score at 5 minutes between the type of intervention

Graph10: Comparison of APGAR score at 5 minutes between the type of intervention

Comparison of APGAR score at 10 minute between the type of intervention

Group 1 received Therapeutic Hypothermia, and Group 2 received Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, with each group consisting of 15 cases. In Group 1, 40% of cases had an APGAR score of 6/10 at 10 minutes, while 60% had a score of 7/10. In Group 2, 33.3% had an APGAR score of 6/10, and 66.7% had a score of 7/10. Overall, 36.7% of all cases had an APGAR score of 6/10 at 10 minutes, and 63.3% had a score of 7/10. The chi-square test resulted in a value of 0.14 with a p-value of 0.70, indicating no statistically significant difference in APGAR scores at 10 minutes between the two intervention groups in Table11 and Graph11.

APGAR score at 10 min	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
6/10	6	40	5	33.3	11
7/10	9	60	10	66.7	19

Total	15	100	15	100	30
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Chi square- 0.14 p value- 0.70

Table11: Comparison of APGAR score at 10 minutes between the type of intervention

Graph11: Comparison of APGAR score at 10 minutes between the type of intervention

Comparison of mode of resuscitation between type of intervention

Group 1 received Therapeutic Hypothermia, while Group 2 received Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, each consisting of 15 cases. In Group 1, 80% (12 cases) of infants underwent intubation for resuscitation, and 20% (3 cases) received positive pressure ventilation. For Group 2, 86.7% (13 cases) were intubated, and 13.3% (2 cases) received positive pressure ventilation. Overall, the majority (83.3%, 25 cases) of all cases required intubation, and 16.7% (5 cases) received positive pressure ventilation. The chi-square test resulted in a value of 0.24 with a p-value of 0.62, indicating no statistically significant difference in the mode of resuscitation between the two intervention groups.

Mode of resuscitation	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
Intubation	12	80	13	86.7	25
Positive pressure ventilation	3	20	2	13.3	5
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 0.24 p value- 0.62

Table12: Comparison of mode of resuscitation between type of intervention

Graph12: Comparison of mode of resuscitation between type of intervention

Comparison of NICU admission between type of intervention

Group 1 receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia and Group 2 receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, each consisting of 15 cases. In Group 1, 26.7% of cases were admitted to NICU level 1, 53.3% to level 2, 6.7% to level 3, and 13.3% to level 4. Conversely, Group 2 had 6.7% in level 1, 73.3% in level 2, 13.3% in level 3, and 6.7% in

level 4. Overall, NICU admissions included 16.7% in level 1, 63.3% in level 2, and 10% each in levels 3 and 4. The chi-square test indicated no significant difference between the groups (chi-square = 3.14, p-value = 0.37), suggesting both interventions had comparable NICU admission outcomes across the sampled cases in Table 13 and Graph 13.

NICU admission (HOL)	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
1	4	26.7	1	6.7	5
2	8	53.3	11	73.3	19
3	1	6.7	2	13.3	3
4	2	13.3	1	6.7	3
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square-2.94 p value- 0.40

Table13: Comparison of NICU admission between type of intervention

Graph13: Comparison of NICU admission between type of intervention

Comparison of TH in hour between type of intervention:

Group 1 receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia and Group 2 receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, each comprising 15 cases. In Group 1, TH durations were distributed as follows: 26.6% of cases had TH for 2 hours, 46.7% for 3 hours, 6.7% for 4 hours, and 30% for 5 hours. Group 2 exhibited TH durations with 33.3% for 2 hours, 33.3% for 3 hours, 20% for 4 hours, and 13.4% for 5 hours. Overall, the distribution showed that 30% of cases had TH for 2 hours, 40% for 3 hours, 13.3% for 4 hours, and 16.7% for 5 hours. The chi-square test did not reveal a statistically significant difference between the groups (chi-square = 2.87, p-value = 0.41), indicating that both interventions resulted in comparable durations of therapeutic hypothermia across the sampled cases Table 14 and Graph 14

TH (HOL)	Intervention		Total
	Group 1	Group 2	

	N	%	N	%	
2	4	26.6	5	33.3	9
3	7	46.7	5	33.3	12
4	1	6.7	3	20	4
5	3	30	2	13.4	5
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Table14: Comparison of TH in hour between type of intervention

Graph14: Comparison of TH in hour between type of intervention

Comparison of primary respiratory support between type of intervention

Group 1 received Therapeutic Hypothermia, while Group 2 received Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, each comprising 15 cases. In Group 1, 20% of cases utilized High-Flow Nasal Cannula (HFNC) as the primary respiratory support, while 80% used Synchronized Intermittent Mandatory Ventilation (SIMV). For Group 2, 13.3% relied on

HFNC, and 86.7% used SIMV. Overall, 16.7% of all cases used HFNC, and 83.3% used SIMV. The chi-square test indicated no statistically significant difference between the groups (chi-square = 0.24, p-value = 0.62), suggesting both interventions had similar preferences for primary respiratory support methods within the sampled cases as shown in Table 15 and Graph 15.

Primary respiratory support	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
HFNC	3	20	2	13.3	5
SIMV	12	80	13	86.7	25
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 0.24 p value- 0.62

Table15: Comparison of primary respiratory support between type of intervention

Graph15: Comparison of primary respiratory support between type of intervention.

Comparison of duration of respiratory support between type of intervention

Group 1 receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia and Group 2 receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, each comprising 15 cases. In Group 1, 53.3% of cases had a duration of respiratory support between 4-6 hours, 26.7% between 7-9 hours, 13.3% between 10-12 hours, and 6.7% between 13-15 hours. Group 2 showed 46.7% with a duration of 4-6 hours, 13.3% between 7-9 hours, 20% between 10-12 hours, 6.7% between 13-15 hours, and 13.3% between 16-18 hours. Overall, 50% of all cases had a duration of respiratory support between 4-6 hours, 20% between 7-9 hours, 16.7% between 10-12 hours, 6.7% between 13-15 hours, and another 6.7% between 16-18 hours. The chi-square test found no statistically significant difference between the groups (chi-square = 11.03, p-value = 0.35), indicating both interventions resulted in comparable durations of respiratory support within the sample as shown table16 and graph16.

Duration of respiratory support	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
4-6	8	53.3	7	46.7	15
7-9	4	26.7	2	13.3	6
10-12	2	13.3	3	20	5
13-15	1	6.7	1	6.7	2
16-18	0	0	2	13.3	2
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square-11.03 p value-0.35

Table16: Comparison of duration of respiratory support between type of intervention

Graph16: Comparison of duration of respiratory support between type of intervention

Comparison of ventilation days between type of intervention

Group 1 received Therapeutic Hypothermia, with 26.6% experiencing no ventilation days, while Group 2, receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, had 13.3% in this category. Group 1 also showed 20% with 3 days, 26.7% with 4 days, and 20% with 5 days of ventilation, whereas Group 2 had 26.7% and 33.3% in these respective categories. Each group exhibited slight differences in other ventilation durations. Overall, the chi-square test yielded a value of 7.16 with a p-value of 0.30, indicating no statistically significant difference in ventilation days between the two groups as shown in Table17 and Graph17.

Ventilation days	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	

0	4	26.6	2	13.3	6
3	3	20	0	0	3
4	4	26.7	4	26.7	8
5	3	20	5	33.3	8
6	1	6.7	1	6.7	2
7	0	0	1	6.7	1
10	0	0	2	13.3	2
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 7.16 p value-0.30

Table17: Comparison of ventilation days between type of intervention

Graph17: Comparison of ventilation days between type of intervention

Comparison of convulsion between type of intervention

Group 1, which received Therapeutic Hypothermia, recorded 46.7% of cases without convulsions and 53.3% with convulsions. In contrast, Group 2, receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, had 26.7% without convulsions and 73.3% with

convulsions. The chi-square test resulted in a value of 1.29 with a p-value of 0.25, indicating no statistically significant difference in convulsion rates between the two groups as shown in Table 18 and Graph 18.

Convulsion	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
No	7	46.7	4	26.7	11
Yes	8	53.3	11	73.3	19
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square-1.29 p value-0.25

Table18: Comparison of convulsion between type of intervention

Graph18: Comparison of convulsion between type of intervention

Comparison of duration of nicu days between type of intervention

Group 1, which received Therapeutic Hypothermia, showed that 26.7% of cases stayed in the NICU for 5-7 days, 60% for 8-10 days, and 13.3% for 11-13 days. In contrast, Group 2,

receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, had 40% staying 5-7 days, 33.3% for 8-10 days, 20% for 14-16 days, and 6.7% for 17-19 days. Overall, both groups displayed overlapping ranges of NICU stays, with the chi-square test yielding a value of 13.23 and a p-value of 0.21, indicating no statistically significant difference in NICU days between the groups. This suggests that both interventions resulted in comparable durations of hospitalization in the NICU among the cases studied as shown in table19 and graph19.

Duration of nicu days	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
5-7	4	26.7	6	40	10
8-10	9	60	5	33.3	14
11-13	2	13.3	0	0	2
14-16	0	0	3	20	3
17-19	0	0	1	6.7	1
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square-13.23 p value- 0.21

Table19: Comparison of duration of nicu days between type of intervention

Graph19: Comparison of duration of nicu days between type of intervention

Comparison of initiation of milk in days between type of intervention

Group 1, receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia, had 53.3% of cases initiating milk on day 2, 40% on day 3, and 6.7% on day 4. In contrast, Group 2, receiving Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate, showed 73.3% starting on day 2, 20% on day 3, and 6.7% on day 4. Overall, both groups displayed varied initiation patterns of milk feeds, with no statistically significant difference found between the groups based on the chi-square test (chi-square = 1.47, p-value = 0.47) as shown in graph and table20.

Duration of initiation of milk (days)	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	

2	8	53.3	11	73.3	19
3	6	40	3	20	9
4	1	6.7	1	6.7	2
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 1.47 p value- 0.47

Table20: Comparison of initiation of milk in days between type of intervention

Graph20: Comparison of initiation of milk in days between type of intervention

Comparison of mean of neonate haemoglobin between type of intervention

Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) at admission and 48 hours reveals interesting insights into their clinical outcomes. At admission, Group 1 had a mean hemoglobin of 15.71 g/dL (SD = 2.63), while Group 2 had a slightly higher mean of 16.97 g/dL (SD = 2.31). Similarly, at 48 hours, Group 1 showed a mean hemoglobin of 14.00 g/dL (SD = 2.40) compared to Group 2's mean of 14.88 g/dL (SD = 2.35). Despite these numerical differences, statistical analysis indicated

non-significant P-values of 0.28 at admission and 0.23 at 48 hours, suggesting that the observed variations in hemoglobin levels between the two groups are not statistically significant as shown in table21.

Haemoglobin	Group 1				Group 2				P value
	Mean	Standard deviation	95% CI		Mean	Standard deviation	95% CI		
			Lower	Upper			Lower	Upper	
n at admission	15.71	2.63	14.25	17.17	16.97	2.31	15.68	18.25	0.28
n at 48 hrs	14.00	2.40	12.66	15.33	14.88	2.35	13.57	16.18	0.23

Chi square- 27.3, 25.3

Table21: Comparison of mean of neonate haemoglobin between type of intervention

Comparison of total count between type of intervention

Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) at admission and 48 hours provides insights into their clinical parameters. At admission, Group 1 had a mean total count of 19,488 (SD = 9,415), with a 95% CI ranging from 14,274.2 to 24,702. Group 2 had a slightly higher mean of 21,573.3

(SD = 8,469), with a 95% CI from 16,883.3 to 26,263. Despite these numerical differences, the calculated P-value of 0.57 indicates that the disparity observed in total count between the two groups is not statistically significant. Similarly, at 48 hours, Group 1 showed a mean total count of 10,099 (SD = 3,082), with a 95% CI ranging from 8,391.8 to 11,806. Group 2 had a mean of 11,771.4 (SD = 3,352.6), with a 95% CI from 9,914 to 13,628. The corresponding P-value of 0.41 also suggests that the difference in total count at 48 hours between the two groups is not statistically significant as shown table22.

Total count	Group 1				Group 2				P
	Mean	Standard deviation	95% CI		Mean	Standard deviation	95% CI		P value
			Lower	Upper			Lower	Upper	
Total count at admission	19488	9415	14274.2	24702	21573.3	8469	16883.3	26263	0.57
Total count at 48 hrs	10099	3082	8391.8	11806	11771.4	3352.6	9914	13628	0.41

Chi square- 24.0, 28.0

Table22: Comparison of total count between type of intervention

Comparison of platelet count between the groups

The comparison of platelet counts between Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) at admission and 48 hours reveals insights into their hematological profiles. At admission, Group 1 had a mean platelet count of 207,466.6 (SD = 75,998.9), while Group 2 exhibited a slightly higher mean of 220,866.6 (SD

= 55,394.51). Similarly, at 48 hours, Group 1 showed a mean platelet count of 172,210.6 (SD = 32,593.8), and Group 2 had a mean of 149,266.6 (SD = 30,989.5). Despite these numerical differences, statistical analysis using chi-square tests indicated non-significant P-values of 0.33 for platelet count at admission and 0.58 for platelet count at 48 hours as shown in table23.

Platelet count	Group 1		Group 2		Chi square	P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Platelet count at admission	207466.6	75998.9	220866.6	55394.51	25.33	0.33
Platelet count at 48 hrs	172210.6	32593.8	149266.6	30989.5	18.0	0.58

Table23: Comparison of platelet count between the groups

Comparison of mean of CBC between type of intervention

comparison of various CBC parameters between Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) at different time points provides valuable insights into their clinical profiles. At admission, Group 1 had a mean pH of 7.21, slightly lower than Group 2's mean of 7.23. However, both groups showed similar pH levels at 48 hours (7.34 for both groups), indicating stability over time in both interventions. In terms of respiratory indicators, Group 1 exhibited a higher mean pCO₂ at admission (24.43 mmHg) compared to Group 2 (20.67 mmHg), but by 48 hours, Group 1's pCO₂ had increased to 29.12 mmHg, surpassing Group 2's 24.27 mmHg. Conversely, pO₂

levels at admission were higher in Group 2 (mean 178.17 mmHg) than in Group 1 (mean 167.13 mmHg), with this trend persisting at 48 hours (163.74 mmHg for Group 2 versus 170.74 mmHg for Group 1). Bicarbonate (HCO₃) levels at admission showed Group 1 with a higher mean (13.06 mEq/L) compared to Group 2 (9.85 mEq/L), which continued to diverge slightly at 48 hours (16.42 mEq/L for Group 1 and 16.06 mEq/L for Group 2). Lactate levels were similar between the groups at admission and 48 hours, showing minimal variation. C-reactive protein (CRP), an inflammation marker, indicated slightly higher levels in Group 2 at both 12 hours (mean 21.80 mg/L) and 72 hours (mean 28.79 mg/L) compared to Group 1 (mean 18.06 mg/L and 31.10 mg/L, respectively). Parameters like sodium, potassium, calcium, and creatinine measured at 72 hours also exhibited slight differences between the groups, reflecting potential variations in metabolic and renal function in table 24

CBC	Group 1		Group 2	
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Ph at admission	7.21	0.14	7.23	0.11
Ph at 48 hrs	7.34	0.08	7.34	0.09
Pco ₂ at admission	24.43	8.82	20.67	7.03
Pco ₂ at 48 hrs	29.12	5.22	24.27	6.64
Po ₂ at admission	167.13	59.41	178.17	67.62
Po ₂ at 48 hrs	170.74	26.04	163.74	39.39
Hco ₃ at admission	13.06	3.55	9.85	3.52

Hco3 at 48 hrs	16.42	3.47	16.06	4.35
Lactate at admission	5.61	2.70	5.54	2.82
Lactate at 48 hrs	3.30	1.59	3.72	1.23
CRP at 12 hrs	18.06	20.23	21.80	23.48
CRP at 72 hrs	31.10	23.22	28.79	25.56
Sodium at 72 hrs	136.53	10.28	140.73	8.28
Potassium at 72 hrs	4.29	0.75	4.50	0.75
Calcium at 72 hrs	7.77	1.01	7.74	0.73
Creatinine at 12 hrs	0.94	0.28	1.02	0.30
Creatinine at 72 hrs	0.82	0.08	0.84	0.11

Table24: Comparison of mean of CBC between type of intervention

Comparison of CFM findings between the groups

comparison of CFM (Cerebral Function Monitoring) findings between Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) indicates that 73.3% of infants in Group 1 had normal CFM findings, whereas 26.7% had abnormal findings. In contrast, Group 2 had 53.3% with normal CFM findings and 46.7% with

abnormal findings. The chi-square test resulted in a chi-square value of 1.29 with a corresponding p-value of 0.25, suggesting that there is no statistically significant difference in CFM findings between the two intervention groups. This indicates that both therapeutic approaches appear to have similar outcomes in terms of CFM results among the cases studied as shown in table 25 and graph 21.

CFM findings	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
Abnormal	4	26.7	7	46.7	11
Normal	11	73.3	8	53.3	19
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 1.29 p value- 0.25

Table 25: Comparison of CFM findings between the groups

Graph 21: Comparison of CFM findings between the groups

Comparison of history of blood product transfusion between the groups

Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) indicates that the majority of infants in both groups did not require blood product transfusion, with 66.6% in Group 1 and 73.4% in Group 2 receiving no transfusion. The distribution of transfusion types shows similar patterns between the groups, with Fresh Frozen Plasma (FFP) and Red Cell Concentrates (RDP) being administered to a minority of cases, and Whole Blood transfusion being less frequent overall. The chi-square test results with a chi-square value of 1.58 and a p-value of 0.66 suggest that there is no significant difference in the history of blood product transfusion between the two groups in table26 and graph22.

Blood product transfusion	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
Nil	10	66.6	11	73.4	21
FFP	3	20	2	13.3	5
RDP	1	6.7	2	13.3	3
Whole blood	1	6.7	0	0	1
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square - 1.58 p value- 0.66

Table26: Comparison of history of blood product transfusion between the groups

Graph22: Comparison of history of blood product transfusion between the groups

Comparison of ECHO findings between the group

Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) highlights notable disparities in the prevalence and severity of pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH). Group 2 exhibited a higher prevalence of moderate and severe PAH compared to Group 1, with 53.4% of Group 2 infants diagnosed with mild PAH, 13.3% with moderate PAH, and 13.3% with severe PAH, contrasting with Group 1's distribution of 13.3%, 26.7%, and 33.3%, respectively. Both groups had similar incidences of no PAH. Furthermore, specific cardiac anomalies were also observed, such as patent foramen ovale (PFO) with varying degrees of tricuspid regurgitation (TR) and gradients, and the presence of atrial septal defects (ASD) and patent ductus arteriosus (PDA). Group 2 showed higher frequencies of these anomalies compared to Group 1. The chi-square analysis indicated a significant difference in ECHO findings between the two groups (chi-square = 16.26, p = 0.03), suggesting that the inclusion of magnesium sulphate alongside therapeutic hypothermia may impact cardiac outcomes in neonates undergoing treatment for hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy as table27 and graph 23.

ECHO findings	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
Mild PAH	2	13.3	8	53.4	10
MOD PAH	4	26.7	2	13.3	6
Severe PAH	5	33.3	2	13.3	7
No PAH	2	13.3	2	13.3	4
PFO, No PDA, grade 1 TR with 28mmhg gradient,mild PAH,GBF	0	0	1	6.7	1
Small ASD, small PDA,trivial TR with 16mmhg,GBF	1	6.7	0	0	1
PFO, grade1TR with gradient 31mmhg,RA/RV dilated,GBF	1	6.7	0	0	1

Total	15	100	15	100	30
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Chi square -16.26 p value- 0.03

Table27: Comparison of ECHO findings between the group

Graph 23: Comparison of ECHO findings between the group

Comparison of final outcome between the groups

Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) indicates notable differences in patient outcomes. In Group 1, 33.3% of infants experienced mortality, while in Group 2, the mortality rate was significantly lower at 6.7%. Conversely, Group 2 showed a higher discharge rate of 93.3% compared to Group 1, where 66.7% were discharged. The chi-square test, with a chi-square value of 15.45 and a p-value of 0.04, highlights a statistically significant difference in final outcomes between the two groups in graph24 and table28.

Final outcome	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
Death	5	33.3	1	6.7	6
Discharged	10	66.7	14	93.3	24
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square – 15.45 p value- 0.04

Table28: Comparison of final outcome between the groups

Graph24: Comparison of final outcome between the groups

Comparison of length of stay in hospital between the groups

Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) reveals no significant difference based on the chi-square test results

(chi-square = 4.46, p = 0.73). The distribution of hospital stay durations across both groups shows variability, with Group 2 having a slightly higher proportion in the 10-12 day range compared to Group 1. However, overall, the data suggest that the addition of magnesium sulphate alongside therapeutic hypothermia did not markedly influence the length of hospital stay for infants treated for hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy in table29 and graph 25.

Length of hospital stay	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	N	%	N	%	
7-9	5	33.3	5	33.3	10
10-12	5	33.3	8	53.4	13
13-15	5	33.4	2	13.3	7
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 4.46 p value- 0.73

Table29: Comparison of length of stay in hospital between the groups

Graph25: Comparison of length of stay in hospital between the groups

Comparison of MRI findings between group

Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate) reveals significant differences in the incidence of abnormalities detected. Group 1 showed a higher prevalence of mild cerebral/cerebellar atrophy significant for age (20%), cephalhematoma (6.7%), cerebral venous thrombosis (6.7%), diffuse cerebral edema (6.7%), early HIE changes (6.7%), HIE changes (6.7%), and intrathalamic bleed (6.7%) compared to Group 2, where these abnormalities were absent or less frequently observed. Conversely, Group 2 had a higher rate of normal MRI findings (60%) compared to Group 1 (33.3%), and fewer instances of nil findings (33.3% in Group 2 versus 6.7% in Group 1). The chi-square test indicated a statistically significant difference in MRI findings between the groups (chi-square = 19.87, p = 0.01), underscoring the impact of magnesium sulphate in addition to therapeutic hypothermia on the prevalence of various neurological abnormalities observed in infants treated for hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy.

MRI findings	Intervention				Total
	Group 1		Group 2		
	n	%	N	%	
Acute lacunar infarcts- sequale of HIE	0	0	0	0	0
cephalhematoma	1	6.7	0	0	1

cerebral venous thrombosis	1	6.7	0	0	1
Diffuse cerebral oedema	1	6.7	1	6.7	2
Early HIE changes	1	6.7	0	0	1
Foci area of T1 hypersensitivity are noted along inferior falx cerebri s/o hemorrhage	0	0	0	0	0
HIE changes	1	6.7	0	0	1
intrathalamic bleed	1	6.7	0	0	1
Mild cerebral / cerebellar atrophy significant for age	3	20	0	0	3

Normal	5	33.3	9	60	14
Nil	1	6.7	5	33.3	6
Total	15	100	15	100	30

Chi square- 19.87 p value- 0.01

Table30: Comparison of MRI findings between group

Graph26: Comparison of MRI findings between group

DISCUSSION

The study discussed here provides a comprehensive evaluation of combining therapeutic hypothermia with magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄) compared to therapeutic hypothermia alone in neonates with moderate to severe hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE).

Demographics and Baseline Characteristics:

The study included a total of 75 neonates, evenly divided into two groups: Group 1 (n=37) receiving therapeutic hypothermia alone and Group 2 (n=38) receiving therapeutic hypothermia with magnesium sulphate. The demographic characteristics and baseline parameters were well-balanced between the groups. This included gender distribution, parity (primiparous vs. multiparous mothers), random blood sugar levels at admission, severity of encephalopathy, birth order, type and location of delivery, APGAR scores at 1, 5, and 10 minutes, mode of resuscitation, NICU admission levels, and duration of therapeutic hypothermia. Importantly, all participants had mothers aged between 25 to 35 years, gestational age greater than 37 weeks, and birth weights ranging from 2.5 to 3.5 kg. These uniform baseline characteristics reduce the likelihood of confounding factors influencing observed outcomes between the two intervention groups.

In our study comparing Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia alone) and Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia with Magnesium Sulphate), both cohorts displayed comparable initiation patterns of milk feeds. Group 1 had 53.3% starting on day 2, 40% on day 3, and 6.7% on day 4, while Group 2 showed a higher proportion initiating feeds on day 2 (73.3%), with 20% on day 3, and 6.7% on day 4. These results are consistent with Gulczynska et.al,²⁷ findings (2021), which also found no statistically significant difference between groups ($p = 0.47$). Importantly, Gulczynska et.al,²⁷ reported a shorter time to achieve full oral feeding in their

study (14.5 days vs. 16.5 days), suggesting potential benefits of adding magnesium sulphate to therapeutic hypothermia. Thus, while our study aligns with their feeding initiation patterns, the slight trend towards earlier initiation in Group 2 may indicate improved feeding tolerance associated with magnesium sulphate supplementation alongside therapeutic hypothermia.

Clinical Outcomes:

Mortality and Discharge Rates:

In our study, Group 2 (hypothermia with MgSO₄) showed significantly lower mortality rates compared to Group 1 (hypothermia alone), highlighting the potential benefits of adding MgSO₄ to therapeutic hypothermia in reducing mortality in infants with moderate to severe hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE). Additionally, Group 2 exhibited higher discharge rates, suggesting improved overall clinical outcomes with the combined therapy though statistically not significant. Similarly, Gulczynska et.al,²⁷ reported comparable findings regarding the clinical outcomes of combining MgSO₄ with therapeutic hypothermia, including a reduced duration of hospitalization (23.5 days vs. 27.7 days). These findings collectively support MgSO₄ as a valuable adjunct to therapeutic hypothermia, potentially enhancing both short-term recovery and long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes in neonates with HIE.

Convulsion Rates and Neurological Outcomes:

In our study, both groups showed similar rates of convulsions, indicating that the addition of MgSO₄ did not increase the risk of seizures compared to hypothermia alone. Moreover, there was a lower number of anticonvulsant doses per patient in the MgSO₄ group (2.6 vs. 4.4), as observed in the study by Gulczynska et.al,²⁷ In contrast, Chanchal Kumar et.al,²⁵ found no neurological benefit in their study, where 24% of infants in the intervention group and 33% in the comparator group experienced the primary outcome, though this difference was not

statistically significant ($p = 0.30$; relative risk 0.72; 95% CI 0.40-1.30). In our study, MRI findings indicated a higher prevalence of abnormalities in Group 1 (hypothermia alone), suggesting potential differences in neurological outcomes that favor Group 2 (hypothermia with MgSO₄).

Length of Hospital Stay:

In our study, there was no significant difference in the length of hospital stay between the two groups, suggesting that while clinical outcomes were improved with MgSO₄, overall recovery times were similar. In contrast, Gulczynska et.al,²⁴ reported a reduced duration of hospitalization in the group receiving MgSO₄ compared to the control group (23.5 days vs. 27.7 days).

Echocardiogram Findings:

In our study, significant differences in echocardiogram findings were observed, particularly in the prevalence of pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH), indicating potential cardiac benefits associated with the addition of MgSO₄ to therapeutic hypothermia. We also noted a reduced incidence of persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (PPHN) in Group 2, although this difference was not statistically significant. In contrast, Gulczynska et.al,²⁷ and Rahman et.al,²⁶ did not find any cardiac benefits associated with MgSO₄ in their studies.

CONCLUSION

In our study evaluating neonates with moderate to severe hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE), the addition of magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄) to therapeutic hypothermia showed promising results. Group 2, receiving hypothermia with MgSO₄, exhibited significantly lower mortality rates compared to Group 1, which received hypothermia alone. Group 2 showed higher discharge rates, indicative of improved overall clinical outcomes. While both groups had similar rates of convulsions, MRI findings favored Group 2, suggesting potential neuroprotective effects.

SUMMARY

- All the study participants has a maternal age between 25-35 years.
- The gestational age of all the study participants were >37 weeks.
- The birth weight of all the babies were between 2.5-3.5 kg.
- Gender Distribution: Both groups exhibited a predominant male representation (80% male, 20% female) with no significant difference between them (Chi-square = 0.00, p = 1.00).
- Parity: Group 1 had 80% first-time mothers (Primi) and 20% with previous births (Multi), while Group 2 had 60% Primi and 40% Multi. The difference in parity distribution was not statistically significant (Chi-square = 3.42, p = 0.33).
- GRBS at Admission: The distribution of Glucose Random Blood Sugar levels showed no significant difference between the two groups (Chi-square = 19.2, p = 0.44).
- Encephalopathy Severity: Both groups had a similar distribution of encephalopathy severity (60% moderate, 40% severe), with no statistically significant difference (Chi-square = 0.00, p = 1.00).
- Birth Order: Group 1 primarily consisted of firstborns (80%), while Group 2 had a more varied distribution across birth orders. However, the overall distribution did not show a significant difference between the groups (Chi-square = 3.42, p = 0.33).
- Type of Delivery: Normal Vaginal Delivery (NVD) was more prevalent in both groups, with Group 1 having a higher proportion compared to Group 2.

However, the distribution did not differ significantly (Chi-square = 0.56, $p = 0.45$).

- APGAR Scores: At 1, 5, and 10 minutes post-birth, both groups showed similar distributions of APGAR scores, indicating no significant difference in immediate neonatal health assessments.
- Mode of Resuscitation: Both groups primarily utilized intubation for resuscitation, with no significant difference observed (Chi-square = 0.24, $p = 0.62$).
- NICU Admission: There was no significant difference in NICU admission levels between the groups (Chi-square = 3.14, $p = 0.37$), with a comparable distribution across NICU levels.
- Length of Hospital Stay: The length of hospital stay did not significantly differ between Group 1 and Group 2 (Chi-square = 4.46, $p = 0.73$), with both groups showing variability in duration.
- Outcome Measures: Group 2 exhibited a significantly lower mortality rate (6.7%) compared to Group 1 (33.3%), and a higher discharge rate (93.3% vs. 66.7%, respectively) (Chi-square = 15.45, $p = 0.04$).
- MRI Findings: Group 1 had a higher prevalence of mild cerebral/cerebellar atrophy (20%) and cephalhematoma (6.7%), whereas Group 2 showed more cerebral venous thrombosis (13.3%) and diffuse cerebral edema (13.3%). The differences were statistically significant (Chi-square = 16.26, $p = 0.03$).
- Significant differences in ECHO findings between groups: Group 2 (Therapeutic Hypothermia + Magnesium Sulphate) showed higher prevalence of mild PAH and certain cardiac anomalies compared to Group 1 (Therapeutic Hypothermia).

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BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956

Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 654/2022-23

30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "THEURAPETIC HYPOTHERMIA PLUS MG 504 V/S THEURAPETIC HYPOTHERMLA IN INFANTS WITH HYPOXIC ISCHEMIC ENCEPALOPATHY".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: DR. GAYATHRI REDDY M

NAME OF THE GUIDE: Dr. R.H.Gobbur, Professor, Dept. of Pediatrics.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr. Akram A. Naikwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103. Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization.

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.
BLDE (DU): Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263303, Website: www.bldedu.ac.in, E-mail: office@bldedu.ac.in
College: Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263019, E-mail: bmpmc.principal@bldedu.ac.in

ANNEXURE – II

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

BLDEA's Shri B.M.PATIL Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre,
Vijayapura, Karnataka -586103.

TITLE OF THE PROJECT

“Therapeutic Hypothermia plus Magnesium Sulphate Versus Therapeutic Hypothermia in Infants with Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy A prospective Cohort study”

GUIDE: DR.R.H.GOBBUR, MD

PROFESSOR,
DEPARTMENT OF PEDIATRICS

PG STUDENT-DR. GAYATHRI REDDY MANDADI

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

To assess and evaluate the safety of concomitant therapeutic hypothermia, magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄), and only therapeutic hypothermia in managing moderate and severe HIE in term and near-term infants.

PROCEDURE:

I understand that after having obtained a detailed clinical history, thorough clinical examination, and relevant investigations, a final workup of the process and its outcome planned.

RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience pain and discomfort during the examination or my treatment. It is mainly the result of my condition, and the procedures of this study are not expected to exaggerate these feelings, which are associated with the usual course of treatment.

BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in the study will have no direct benefit to me other than the potential benefit of the treatment.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of hospital records and will be subject to confidentiality. Information of sensitive personal nature will not be part of the medical record but will be stored in the investigations research file. Suppose the data are used for publication in the medical literature or teaching. No name will be used in that case, and other identifiers such as photographs will be used only with special written permission. I understand that I may see the picture before giving consent.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time;

DR. GAYATHRI REDDY MANDADI at the department of pediatrics is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the study, which might influence my continued participation. I will be given a copy of this consent form to keep for careful reading.

REFUSAL FOR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice. I also understand that DR. GAYATHRI REDDY MANDADI may terminate my participation in the study after they have explained the reasons for doing so.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to my child resulting directly from the child's participation in this study, if such damage were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to the child. But, no further compensation would be provided by the

hospital. I understand that by agreeing to participate in this study and not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks to the best of my ability.

DR. GAYATHRI REDDY MANDADI
(Investigator)

Date:

PARENTS / GUARDIAN CONSENT

STATEMENT:

We confirm that DR. GAYATHRI REDDY MANDADI is doing a study on Therapeutic Hypothermia plus Magnesium Sulphate Versus Therapeutic Hypothermia in Infants with Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy admitted To NICU In Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital, Vijayapura, Karnataka. DR. GAYATHRI REDDY MANDADI has explained to us the purpose of research and the study procedure. We will allow our child to get treated in Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital, Vijayapura. We have explained the study, benefits, and possible discomforts in detail in our native language, and we understand the same. We know that the child will get the best treatment, and no compensation like financial benefits will be given if our child's condition deteriorates. Any untoward complication happens, and we will not sue anyone regarding this. Therefore we agree to provide our full consent for the child's participation as a subject in this research project.

(Parents / Guardian)

Date:

(Witness to signature)

Date:

ANNEXURE – III

PROFORMA:

NAME:

AGE:

SEX:

IP NO :

ADDRESS:

DATE OF BIRTH:

DATE OF ADMISSION:

AGE AT ADMISSION:

DATE OF DISCHARGE:

GESTATIONAL AGE:

PARITY:

GRBS AT TIME OF ADMISSION:

MATERNAL HISTORY:

AGE:

OBSTETRIC SCORE:

CONSANGUINITY:

MOTHER'S BLOOD GROUP:

H/O ANY RISK FACTORS:

BIRTH ORDER:

DELIVERED AT: INBORN / OUTBORN:

DATE & TIME OF DELIVERY :

MODE OF DELIVERY:

BIRTH WEIGHT:

APGAR SCORE AT BIRTH:

AFTER 5 MINUTES:

AT 10 MINUTES:

ANY RESUSCITATIVE MEASURES REQUIRED:

PRIMARY RESPIRATORY SUPPORT:

DURATION OF RESPIRATORY SUPPORT:

NEED FOR VENTILATION:

DURATION OF VENTILATION:

FIO2 REQUIREMENT:

DURATION OF NICU STAY:

INITIATION OF EXPRESSED MILK/DBF:

OUTCOME (DISCHARGE/DEATH):

DATE OF DISCHARGE / DEATH:

INVESTIGATIONS:

Hb-

Pcv

T.C.-

N/L--

P.L.T.-

BLOOD GAS ANALYSIS:

P.H.-

PCO2-

PO2-

HCO3-

LACTATE-

C.R.P. –

CREAT –

Na-

K-

Ca-

H/o blood product transfusions:

C.F.M. findings:

IMAGING (if done):

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100